

CORRELATING TEACHER'S ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-LEARNING AND MENTAL WELLBEING OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE DIVISION OF QUEZON

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 9

Pages: 1183-1189

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2222

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13336618

Manuscript Accepted: 08-13-2024

Correlating Teacher's Attitude towards E-learning and Mental Wellbeing of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Quezon

Ciara Georgette P. Urtal*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between elementary school teachers' attitudes towards e-learning and their mental wellbeing in the Division of Quezon. Based in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Fred Davis and Seligman's PERMAH theory of wellbeing, the research explores how teachers' perceptions of the usefulness, ease of use, and overall acceptance of e-learning impact their emotional and psychological states. The data for this study were collected using a descriptive-correlational method from a randomly selected sample of 346 classroom teachers. The findings of this study reveal that teachers generally have positive attitudes towards e-learning, especially regarding personalized learning and flexibility. However, concerns about accessibility and affordability still exist. The scores for mental wellbeing indicate that teachers are generally coping well, showing high levels of positive emotions, engagement, meaning, relationships, and continuous personal growth. The study also found significant positive correlations between attitudes towards e-learning and mental wellbeing, particularly in relation to personalized learning and engagement. In conclusion, this study emphasizes the need for improved accessibility and engaging resources in e-learning. It recommends projects aimed at enhancing attitudes towards e-learning, comprehensive wellness programs, and ongoing technical support for teachers. Additionally, further research on barriers to effective e-learning implementation is suggested to enhance teacher training programs. Overall, this research highlights the importance of supporting teachers in both their adoption of e-learning and their mental wellbeing. It advocates for integrated approaches that can improve educational and personal outcomes.

Keywords: *classroom teachers, teachers' attitude, e-learning, mental wellbeing, open university system, master's in education management, correlation*

Introduction

The integration of e-learning technologies in education has revolutionized teaching and learning, offering fresh potential and constraints for educators worldwide. However, the mental wellbeing of elementary school teachers is a critical concern. Technology experts continuously develop and advance technology for various applications, including transportation, health, communication, and especially education. E-learning platforms are essential tools for curriculum delivery, engaging learners, and fostering interactive learning experiences. However, educators face challenges such as adapting to modern technologies, managing online classrooms, and addressing diverse learners needs.

Globally, schools may suspend classes due to weather events, emergencies, natural disasters, facility issues, pandemics, strikes, or transportation disruptions. Suspensions can impact learners' learning and academic performance, resulting in lost instructional time. Alternative learning opportunities and support can help mitigate these negative effects, ensuring schools are prepared for future crises and maintain a healthy learning environment (Lasco, 2024).

Meanwhile, teachers' attitudes towards e-learning are crucial in shaping learners' foundational learning experiences in elementary schools to lessen those negative effects. Factors impacting teachers' attitudes towards e-learning include personalized learning, flexibility, accessibility, and engaging resources. It found that these factors collectively enhance teachers' positive attitudes and openness to incorporating e-learning into their instructional methods.

On the other hand, digital learning is a popular alternative to managing education access constraints, but its successful implementation relies heavily on teachers' support and attitudes. Studies on teachers' outlook towards e-learning in higher education have shown positive attitudes in Tamil Nadu, India, and Macedonia, while disapproval in Jordan (Almaiah, 2018). In Asian countries (Lau, 2020), elite universities have transitioned to remote learning due to fast internet access.

Cultural and socioeconomic differences make it difficult for the Philippine education system to adopt digital learning methodologies. Numerous factors, such as accessibility to resources, training opportunities, institutional support, and socioeconomic background, influence teachers' perceptions and experiences with e-learning (Salinas, 2020). However, there is limited empirical evidence on these variables in elementary schools. The COVID-19 pandemic has worsened existing inequalities, including unequal access to technology, limited internet connectivity, and varying levels of technological proficiency among educators. The mental wellbeing of classroom teachers is a critical concern due to the additional stressors and uncertainties associated with e-learning modalities (Cavioni et al., 2023). In light of these challenges, the Department of Education has launched the Digital Rise Program. This initiative aims to foster innovation and digitization in the K-12 curriculum, bridge the gap between the curriculum and information and communication technology (ICT), promote digital literacy competence, and integrate e-learning resources for each subject covered in the curriculum.

The study by McQuaid (2021), which emphasizes the significance of wellbeing in navigating the work and life challenges of teachers and enabling intellectual, emotional, social, and physical flourishing, serves as an inspiration for this research.

However, despite the integration of online education in educational settings, there is an absence of understanding regarding the various connection between teachers' perspectives on e-learning and their mental health. Studies have primarily focused on the adoption of technology or instructional strategies, with little attention given to the potential impact on teachers' psychological and emotional wellbeing. This research gap calls for a comprehensive investigation into how teachers' perceptions, preferences, and experiences with e-learning tools and platforms may influence their mental wellbeing, encompassing elements like positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, accomplishments, and health. Exploring this connection could provide significant knowledge for the enhancement of supportive policies and interventions designed to foster a positive e-learning environment for teachers.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this research was to determine the teachers' attitudes towards e-learning and mental wellbeing in the Division of Quezon. Specifically, the researcher aimed to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the teachers' attitude towards e-learning, along with:
 - 1.1 personalized learning;
 - 1.2 flexibility;
 - 1.3 accessibility; and
 - 1.4 engaging resources?
2. How do the teachers perceive their mental wellbeing in terms of:
 - 2.1 positive emotion;
 - 2.2 engagement;
 - 2.3 relationship;
 - 2.4 meaning;
 - 2.5 achievement; and
 - 2.6 health?
3. Is there any significant relationship between the teachers' attitude towards e-learning and their perceptions about their mental wellbeing?

Literature Review

Teachers' Attitude Towards e-Learning

Радчикова, Odintsova, and Сорокова (2023) highlighted that teachers generally have a positive attitude towards e-learning and are eager to incorporate digital educational environments (DEE) and distance learning, influenced by factors such as professional experience, self-regulation, and personality traits. However, their abilities do not significantly impact their online teaching attitudes. In the Philippines, teachers' attitudes towards e-learning vary, with some favoring it while others doubt its viability as a replacement for in-person learning. The Technology Acceptance Model by Davis (1986) is a key framework for understanding these attitudes, emphasizing the importance of perceived usefulness and ease of use. Aldosemani (2023) further confirmed that ease of use, usefulness, and other factors influence teachers' acceptance of e-learning. Personalized learning and flexible teaching schedules, as discussed by Evanick (2023) and Ripiceanu (2023), are also crucial for enhancing teachers' acceptance of e-learning. Accessibility, interactive and engaging resources, and professional development opportunities are vital for promoting positive teacher attitudes towards e-learning.

Teachers' Mental Wellbeing

The mental wellbeing of teachers is crucial for fostering effective educational environments, as it directly influences their ability to provide quality education and maintain a positive classroom atmosphere. High levels of stress and burnout among teachers can lead to disengagement, reduced student achievement, and increased behavioral issues, highlighting the importance of supporting educators' mental health. Seligman's (2011) PERMA theory, which includes elements such as positive emotion, engagement, relationships, meaning, and achievement, offers a framework for enhancing teacher wellbeing and overall effectiveness. Additionally, the PERMAH model adds health as a key factor in wellbeing, emphasizing the role of physical and mental health in fostering resilience, motivation, and satisfaction in teachers. Studies, such as those by Violago et al. (2023) and Peterson (2021), underscore the significance of psychological wellbeing, emotion regulation, and supportive workplace environments in mitigating burnout and promoting job satisfaction. The urgent need to address teachers' mental health, as noted by Clarion et al. (2023) and Casanova et al. (2022), is particularly relevant in the context of the Philippines, where public school teachers experience mild anxiety, depression, and moderate stress levels. Supporting teacher wellbeing through comprehensive approaches is essential for creating stable and productive educational settings (Seligman, 2011; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017; Violago et al., 2023).

Synthesis of the Reviewed Literature and Studies

The studies explored the relationship between teachers' attitudes towards e-learning and their mental wellbeing, revealing both benefits

and challenges. Positive attitudes towards e-learning can enhance mental wellbeing by offering innovative teaching methods and reducing workloads, while security issues and inadequate facilities can lead to stress (Isroani et al., 2022; Jayanthi et al., 2023; Kruse et al., 2022). The research identifies a need for comprehensive support systems and improved infrastructure to optimize these benefits and mitigate challenges. Additionally, the gap in understanding how personality traits, cultural backgrounds, and technological proficiency influence this relationship suggests that future research should explore these variables and the long-term impacts of e-learning on teachers' mental health (Cavioni et al., 2023; Thi, 2021; Suyatno et al., 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research methodology to investigate teachers' attitudes towards e-learning and their mental wellbeing. Data was collected through survey questionnaires, specifically designed to align with the research questions and elicit objective responses. The main objective of the study was to categorize teachers' attitudes towards e-learning, analyze their perceptions of mental wellbeing, and present the findings through statistical analysis.

Participants

The research focused on 3,008 elementary teachers in Quezon's Fourth Congressional District. A sample size of 341 was determined using the Cochran formula to ensure a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. However, the study saw participation from 346 respondents, indicating slightly higher engagement than expected. The use of the Cochran formula provided a solid foundation for understanding the population and enabled accurate and comprehensive data analysis. Random sampling was employed to select participants, ensuring that every teacher had an equal chance of being included and enhancing the study's representativeness.

Instruments

The researcher collaborated with her thesis adviser to develop a unique survey questionnaire, which consisted of three key sections. The first section focused on the respondents' profile, including their demographic and professional information. The second section evaluated teachers' attitudes towards e-learning across four dimensions: personalized learning, flexibility, accessibility, and engaging resources. This was done using a five-point Likert scale. The third section assessed teachers' mental wellbeing, covering areas such as positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, achievement, and health. This section was also rated on a five-point Likert scale. To ensure the questionnaire's validity, it was reviewed by four education program supervisors from the Division of Quezon and piloted with 36 teachers from another district. The results of this pilot study yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.888, indicating strong internal consistency.

Ethical Considerations

In addressing the ethical considerations for this study, it was ensured that participants' privacy and confidentiality were rigorously protected. Teachers were provided with a detailed consent form outlining the study's purpose, their role, and how their data would be used, ensuring informed consent. Participation was voluntary, with respondents having the option to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Results

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Teachers' Attitude towards E-learning

The findings of the study are presented in table generated from the thematic analysis.

Table 1. *Teachers' Attitude towards E-learning*

	<i>Sub-Problem</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	Personalized Learning	4.16	Moderately Positive
2	Flexibility	4.17	Moderately Positive
3	Accessibility	3.92	Moderately Positive
4	Engaging Resources	4.04	Moderately Positive
	Grand Mean:	4.07	Moderately Positive

Legend: "Highly Negative (1.00 – 1.50)", "Slightly Negative (1.51 – 2.50)", "Neutral (2.51 – 3.50)", "Moderately Positive (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Positive (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 2. *Teachers' Perception about Mental Wellbeing*

	<i>Sub-Problem</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1	Positive Emotion	4.14	Coping Well

2	Engagement	4.19	Coping Well
3	Relationship	4.12	Coping Well
4.	Meaning	4.12	Coping Well
5.	Achievement	4.21	Coping Well
6.	Health	4.13	Coping Well
Grand Mean:		4.15	Coping Well

Legend: "Overwhelmed (1.00 – 1.50)", "Struggling (1.51 – 2.50)", "Neutral (2.51 – 3.50)", "Coping Well (3.51 – 4.50)", "Thriving (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Teachers' Attitude towards e-Learning and Mental Wellbeing

Aspect of e-learning	Highest in Mental Wellbeing	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Personalized Learning	Engagement	0.6578	Strong Positive Correlation	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant
Flexibility	Engagement	0.6323	Strong Positive Correlation	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant
Accessibility	Positive Emotion	0.4790	Weak Positive Correlation	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant
Engaging Resources	Positive Emotion	0.5860	Strong Positive Correlation	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject

Discussion

Table 1 shows the summary of teachers' attitudes towards e-learning shows an overall moderately positive perspective, with a grand mean of 4.07. The sub-problem of flexibility has the highest mean score of 4.17, indicating that teachers particularly appreciate the adaptable nature of e-learning. Conversely, the sub-problem of accessibility has the lowest mean score of 3.92, suggesting that, although teachers view e-learning access positively, it is slightly less favorable compared to other aspects. These results collectively suggest a generally positive attitude towards e-learning among teachers, with recognition of its benefits in terms of innovation, flexibility, and engagement, although with some reservations regarding its economic feasibility and efficacy in achieving learning outcomes.

This study supports Aldosemani's (2023) study affirming that teachers generally exhibit a positive attitude towards e-learning, recognizing its benefits in terms of innovation, flexibility, and engagement. However, the study by Leontev (2023) highlighted that there are reservations regarding its economic feasibility and efficacy in achieving learning outcomes. The study by Reyes (2023) shows that teachers who have more experience in digital environments and possess certain personality traits like openness to experience and agreeableness are more likely to accept and embrace e-learning.

Meanwhile, Table 2 or the teachers' perceptions of their mental well-being reveal a grand mean of 4.15, interpreted as "Coping Well." The highest mean score, 4.21, for achievement, indicates that teachers feel they are effectively meeting their goals and experiencing personal growth. The lowest mean score, 4.12, shared by both relationship and meaning, suggests these areas, while still positive, are perceived slightly less favorably compared to others. Overall, teachers are coping well across all measured domains of mental well-being. These findings suggest that teachers generally view their mental well-being in a positive light, with high scores reflecting optimism about the future, engagement in meaningful activities, and personal growth. However, areas needing attention include finding a life purpose, receiving support from others, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Hartcher et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of considering individual factors, relational aspects of work, and contextual elements that impact teachers' well-being for sustainable improvements. Additionally, Manjari et al. (2020) propose that providing mental health training to teachers and creating a supportive environment within schools can significantly contribute to the overall well-being of both teachers and students.

On the other hand, Table 3 displays the results of a Spearman Rank analysis, which reveals significant positive correlations between teachers' attitudes towards e-learning and their mental wellbeing across different dimensions. The most notable correlation is observed between personalized learning and engagement, with a coefficient of 0.6578, indicating a strong positive relationship. On the other hand, the weakest correlation, although still significant, is found between accessibility and positive emotion, with a coefficient of 0.4790. These findings are consistent with Zhang et al. (2023), who emphasized that personalized learning and flexibility have the strongest positive correlations with engagement, which are crucial for nurturing teachers' sense of involvement and activity. Furthermore, Pei et al. (2022) pointed out that accessibility has the weakest positive correlation with positive emotion, suggesting the need for improvement in this area to better support teachers' emotional wellbeing.

Conclusion

The research's results led to the following conclusions: Teachers' attitude towards e-learning is moderately positive, with particular emphasis on its innovative nature and potential to enhance teaching strategies and flexibility. However, concerns persist regarding the accessibility and affordability of e-learning resources, as highlighted by lower scores in these areas. Teachers generally view their mental wellbeing positively. The highest scores reflect their optimism about the future, engagement in meaningful activities, feeling loved, leading purposeful lives, continual personal growth, and coping with life's challenges. On the other hand, there are areas that need attention. These include finding a life purpose, engaging on a daily basis, receiving support from others, self-judgment based on personal values, achieving important goals, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Teachers' attitudes towards different aspects of e-learning have a substantial influence on their mental wellbeing. Personalized learning and flexibility show the strongest positive

correlations with engagement, highlighting the importance of these factors in enhancing teachers' sense of involvement and activity. In contrast, accessibility shows the weakest, though still positive, correlation with positive emotion, indicating a potential area for improvement to better support teachers' emotional wellbeing.

Following the study's conclusion, the following recommendations are proposed: Conduct a project with the goal of improving teachers' attitude of e-learning accessibility and effectiveness. This goal can be attained through offering subsidized access to technical tools and resources, offering comprehensive training sessions, and collaborating with policymakers to prioritize funding for e-learning infrastructure. By doing so, we can boost teachers' confidence and enhance their attitudes towards e-learning. Implementing a wellness program for teachers can greatly enhance their overall wellbeing. This can be achieved by providing regular workshops on purpose and self-discovery, as well as activities that add variety to their daily routines, in order to cultivate positive emotions. Moreover, establishing a peer support network and mentorship program can improve relationships and enable teachers to uphold their personal values. Furthermore, mindfulness and values clarification sessions can enhance self-assessment, while goal-setting workshops and progress tracking tools can aid teachers in accomplishing significant objectives. Promoting a healthy lifestyle through fitness challenges and offering health resources can create a supportive environment for teachers. Provide comprehensive training and ongoing technical support to teachers. Moreover, integrating more interactive and engaging resources within the e-learning environment can enhance teachers' positive emotions and engagement. Considering a proposal to implement regular professional development workshops that focus on effectively utilizing accessible e-learning tools and creating a supportive community for sharing best practices can significantly strengthen these areas. These steps are practical and can be readily implemented to enhance the overall effectiveness of e-learning for teachers. Further research could investigate the "Barriers to Effective Implementation of E-Learning in Teacher Training Programs." This topic would delve into the challenges educational institutions face in integrating e-learning methodologies into teacher training curricula, including technological infrastructure limitations, resistance to change among faculty, inadequate training and support provided to educators as they transition to e-learning platforms, and disparities in access to digital resources among students. Addressing these issues can improve the quality and accessibility of teacher training programs.

References

- Ahmad, R. (2023). Academic Optimism: A study of secondary school teachers' perceptions. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 4(II). [https://doi.org/10.47205/jdss.2023\(4-ii\)02](https://doi.org/10.47205/jdss.2023(4-ii)02)
- Aldosemani, T. I. (2023). A Technology-Acceptance-Model-Based study of the attitudes towards learning management systems among teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Online Pedagogy and Course Design*, 13(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijopcd.325240>
- Butler, J. & Kern, M. L. (2015). The PERMA-Profler: A brief multidimensional measure of flourishing. Available from <http://www.peggykern.org/questionnaires.html>
- Cann, R. F., Riedel-Prabhakar, R., & Powell, D. (2020). A model of positive school leadership to improve teacher wellbeing. *International Journal of Applied Positive Psychology*, 6(2), 195–218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41042-020-00045-5>
- Casanova, B. E. C., Felix, C. a. C., Balingit, N. D. Z., De Vera, A. M. F., Briones, M. D. M., & Aruta, J. J. B. R. (2022). Social support and bidimensional mental health among primary-level teachers during COVID-19 crisis. *International Journal of School & Educational Psychology*, 11(3), 245–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683603.2022.2105998>
- Cavioni, V., Grazzani, I., Ornaghi, V., Agliati, A., Gandellini, S., Cefai, C., Camilleri, L., Bartolo, P. A., Vorkapić, S. T., Golob, L., Πούλου, M., Martinsone, B., Supe, I., Simões, C., Lebre, P., Colomeischi, A., Rusu, P. P., Acostoae, L., Vintur, T., & Conte, E. (2023). A multi-component curriculum to promote teachers' mental health: Findings from the PROMEHs program. *International Journal of Emotional Education*, 15(1), 34–52. <https://doi.org/10.56300/kfnz2526>
- Clarion, E. B., & Palarisan, N. J. (2023). Mental Health of Public School Teachers in Davao de Oro, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 43(2), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2023/v43i2935>
- De Los Arcos, B., Faems, B., Comas-Quinn, A., & Pulker, H. (2017). Teachers' use and acceptance of gamification and social networking features of an open repository. *The European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning*, 20(1), 127–138. <https://doi.org/10.1515/eurodl-2017-0008>
- De Vries, L. P. (2023). Differences in well-being. <https://doi.org/10.5463/thesis.11>
- Desombre, C., Delaval, M., & Jury, M. (2021). Influence of social support on teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.736535>
- Dhingra, A., & Khan, W. S. (2023). The PERMA model of wellbeing. In *Advances in medical diagnosis, treatment, and care (AMDTC) book series* (pp. 71–81). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-7630-7.ch005>
- Duggan, S. (2018). Changes in teacher perception and practice which occur with the implementation of personalized learning using technology. *SciSpace - Paper*. <https://typeset.io/papers/changes-in-teacher-perception-and-practice-which->

- Even-Zahav, A., Widder, M., & Hazzan, O. (2022). From teacher professional development to teacher personal-professional growth: the case of expert STEM teachers. *Teacher Development*, 26(3), 299–316. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2022.2052947>
- Fleetwood, D. (2023). Simple random Sampling: definition and examples. *QuestionPro*. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/simple-random-sampling/>
- Gerona, M. C. G., & Mirasol, R. G. (2022). ATTITUDES OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING DELIVERY IN THE TIME OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC. *International Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, 05(05), 117–142. <https://doi.org/10.37500/ijessr.2022.5508>
- Hartcher, K., Chapman, S., & Morrison, C. (2022). Applying a band-aid or building a bridge: ecological factors and divergent approaches to enhancing teacher wellbeing. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 53(3), 329–356. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764x.2022.2155612>
- Intra, F. S., Nasti, C., Massaro, R., Perretta, A. J., Di Girolamo, A., Brighi, A., & Biroli, P. (2023). Flexible learning environments for a sustainable lifelong learning process for teachers in the school context. *Sustainability*, 15(14), 11237. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151411237>
- Jayanthi, K., Priya, M., Saranya, S., Gomathi, R., & Sam, D. (2023). E-Learning as a desirable form of education in the era of Society 5.0. In *Chapman and Hall/CRC eBooks* (pp. 23–51). <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003322252-2>
- Kasmiran, M. S. (2020). WORTHY OR NOT? TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG INDONESIAN LEARNERS USING TECHNOLOGY IN THE CLASSROOM. *English Language Teaching and Research Journal*, 4(1), 43–52. <https://doi.org/10.37147/eltrj.v4i1.35>
- Kern, M. L. (2022). PERMAH. In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 12–24). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003013778-3>
- Kruse, C., Smith, M., & Clarke, D. (2022). Technology alone does not achieve error reduction - a study of handwritten, tick-sheet, ink stamp and electronic medical prescriptions. *South African Journal of Surgery*, 60(4), 259–267. <https://doi.org/10.17159/2078-5151/sajs3670>
- Lasco, G. (2024, May 24). Rethinking class suspensions. *Asia News Network*. <https://asianews.network/rethinking-class-suspensions/>
- Leontev, M. (2023). Study the attitude of teachers and students toward online classes at technical university. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 381, 02027. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202338102027>
- Lübke, L., Pinguart, M., & Schwinger, M. (2021). The role of flexibility in the realization of inclusive education. *Sustainability*, 13(8), 4452. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084452>
- Magare, I., Graham, M. A., & Eloff, I. (2022). An assessment of the reliability and validity of the PERMA Well-Being Scale for Adult Undergraduate students in an open and distance learning context. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(24), 16886. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192416886>
- Manjari, A., & Srivastava, A. (2020). Teachers and schools as change agents in improving mental health among adolescents. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.25215/0801.092>
- McQuaid, M. (2021, July 1). The PERMAH Wellbeing Survey | Wellbeing | Michelle McQuaid. Michelle McQuaid. <https://www.michellemcquaid.com/permah-workplace-survey/>
- Miksza, P., Shaw, J. T., Richerme, L. K., Hash, P. M., Hodges, D. A., & Parker, E. C. (2023). Quantitative descriptive and correlational research. In *Oxford University Press eBooks* (pp. 241–C12P143). <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197639757.003.0012>
- Morgan, B., & Simmons, L. (2021). A ‘PERMA’ response to the pandemic: an online positive education programme to promote wellbeing in university students. *Frontiers in Education*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.642632>
- Noguera, I., & Vizarreta, P. V. (2022). Teachers’ and students’ perspectives on the intensive use of technology for teaching and learning. *Educar*, 59(1), 213–229. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/educar.1551>
- Nwoko, J. C., Emeto, T. I., Malau-Aduli, A., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2023b). A systematic review of the factors that influence teachers’ occupational wellbeing. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(12), 6070. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20126070>
- Palmer, D. (2020). Teacher enthusiasm and student motivation for learning. *Global Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.5296/gjes.v6i1.16405>
- Patra, P. (2020). Perception of school teachers towards using community resources to enhance scholastic achievement. *International Journal of Applied Research* 2020,6(3),67-68. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/2020/vol6issue3/PartB/6-1-65-889.pdf>

- Pei, S., Chen, Z., Zhang, X., & Guo, J. (2022). An empirical study on the influencing mechanism of Chinese university teachers' wellbeing. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.970593>
- Pinto, I. (2023, October 10). E-learning accessibility: definition, best practices and more. Create an Online Course Easily | Easygenerator. <https://www.easygenerator.com/en/blog/e-learning/elearning-accessibility/#:~:text=To%20put%20it%20simply%2C%20accessibility,%2C%20physical%2C%20or%20learning%20disabilities.>
- Pratiwi, W. R. (2020). The Practice of Digital Learning (D-Learning) in the Study from Home (SFH) Policy: Teachers' Perceptions. *Xinan Jiaotong Daxue Xuebao*, 55(4). <https://doi.org/10.35741/issn.0258-2724.55.4.17>
- Redeş, D. A., & Roman, A. F. (2022). The wellbeing perception of teachers and the impact on learning process of preschoolers. *European Proceedings of Educational Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epes.22032.74>
- Reyes, J. D. C. (2023). Teachers' ability, attitude, and acceptance towards distance learning. *Journal of Digital Educational Technology*, 3(2), ep2307. <https://doi.org/10.30935/jdet/13349>
- Ripiceanu, R. (2023, February 9). A complete guide to flexible teaching - SPARK. SPARK. <https://spark.school/a-complete-guide-to-flexible-teaching/>
- Samson, B. (2023). Teachers' Growth Mindset and Work Engagement: Inputs to the creation of a website for teachers' well-being. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 11(5), 273–278. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-11-5-4>
- Sandholm, D., Simonsen, J., Ström, K., & Fagerlund, Å. (2022). Teachers' experiences with positive education. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 53(2), 237–255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764x.2022.2093839>
- Suyatno, S., Pambudi, D. I., Wantini, W., Abdurrohman, A., & Mardati, A. (2022). The mediating role of meaning at work in promoting teacher commitment and reducing burnout. *Frontiers in Education*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.962163>
- Tarigan, F. N. (2021). Fostering University Students' Attitude toward Utilization of E-Learning. *Journal of Community Service and Research*, 5(2), 52–57. <https://doi.org/10.24114/jcsrc.v5i2.26127>
- Thi, Ngoc, Linh, Ly., Thi, Lam, Nguyen., Huu, Ngoc, Nguyen. (2021). Using E-Learning Platforms in Online Classes: A Survey on Tertiary English Teachers' Perceptions.
- Violago, A. S., & Fabella, F. E. T. (2023). Psychological Well-Being of Junior High School Teachers. *Cognizance Journal*, 3(6), 103–129. <https://doi.org/10.47760/cognizance.2023.v03i06.008>
- Wilson, R., Sellman, E., & Joseph, S. (2023). 'Doing well' and 'being well'—secondary school teachers' perspectives. *British Educational Research Journal*, 49(5), 987–1004. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3878>
- World Health Organization: WHO. (2022). Mental health. [www.who.int. https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-strengthening-our-response#:~:text=Mental%20health%20is%20a%20state,and%20contribute%20to%20their%20community.](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-strengthening-our-response#:~:text=Mental%20health%20is%20a%20state,and%20contribute%20to%20their%20community.)
- Zhang, H., Sun, X., Zhang, Y., Wang, Q., & Yao, C. (2023). Towards personalized instruction: co-designing a Teacher-Centered dashboard for learning engagement analysis in blended learning environments. In *Lecture notes in computer science* (pp. 563–574). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-34411-4_38

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ciara Georgette P. Urtal

Polytechnic University of the Philippines